

Weakly binary $g\alpha$ -locally closed sets in Binary Topological Space

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 25 August 2023	In this paper, we will define $wbga-lc$ -sets, $wbag-lc$ -sets, $wbga-lc^*$ -sets, $wbag-lc^*$ -sets, $wbga-lc^{**}$ -sets, $wbag-lc^{**}$ -sets, $bg^*\alpha-lc$ -sets, $bg^*\alpha-lc^*$ -sets, $bg^*\alpha-lc^{**}$ -sets, $wbg^*\alpha-lc$ -sets, $wbg^*\alpha-lc^*$ -sets and $wbg^*\alpha-lc^{**}$ -sets and study some of their properties. Also we will prove that $bg^*\alpha-lc^*$ -sets and $bg^*\alpha-lc^{**}$ -sets are stronger than $bg^*\alpha-lc$ -sets and weaker than binary locally closed sets.
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I. INTRODUCTION

In 2011, S.Nithyanantha Jothi and P.Thangavelu [8] introduced topology between two sets and also studied some of their properties. For background material, papers [1] to [15] may be perused. In this paper, we will define $wbga-lc$ -sets, $wbag-lc$ -sets, $wbga-lc^*$ -sets, $wbag-lc^*$ -sets, $wbga-lc^{**}$ -sets, $wbag-lc^{**}$ -sets, $bg^*\alpha-lc$ -sets, $bg^*\alpha-lc^*$ -sets, $bg^*\alpha-lc^{**}$ -sets, $wbg^*\alpha-lc$ -sets, $wbg^*\alpha-lc^*$ -sets and $wbg^*\alpha-lc^{**}$ -sets and study some of their properties. Also we will prove that $bg^*\alpha-lc^*$ -sets and $bg^*\alpha-lc^{**}$ -sets are stronger than $bg^*\alpha-lc$ -sets and weaker than binary locally closed sets.

II. WEAKLY BINARY $g\alpha$ -LOCALLY CLOSED SETS AND WEAKLY BINARY αg -LOCALLY CLOSED SETS

Definition 2.1 Let (A, B) be a subset of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$. Then (A, B) is called a

1. weakly binary generalized α -locally closed set (briefly $wbga-lc$ -set) if $(A, B) = (G, H) \cap (E, F)$, where (G, H) is $wbga$ -open and (E, F) is $wbga$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.

2. weakly binary α -generalized locally closed set (briefly $wbag-lc$ -set) if $(A, B) = (G, H) \cap (E, F)$, where (G, H) is $wbag$ -open and (E, F) is $wbag$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.
3. $wbga-lc^*$ -set if $(A, B) = (G, H) \cap (E, F)$, where (G, H) is $wbga$ -open and (E, F) is binary closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.
4. $wbag-lc^*$ -set if $(A, B) = (G, H) \cap (E, F)$, where (G, H) is $wbag$ -open and (E, F) is binary closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.
5. $wbga-lc^{**}$ -set if $(A, B) = (G, H) \cap (E, F)$, where (G, H) is binary open and (E, F) is $wbga$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.
6. $wbag-lc^{**}$ -set if $(A, B) = (G, H) \cap (E, F)$, where (G, H) is binary open and (E, F) is $wbag$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.

The collection of all $wbga-lc$ -sets (resp. $wbga-lc^*$ -sets, $wbga-lc^{**}$ -sets, $wbag-lc$ -sets, $wbag-lc^*$ -sets and $wbag-lc^{**}$ -sets) of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ will be denoted by $WBG\alpha LC(X, Y)$ (resp. $WBG\alpha LC^*(X, Y)$, $WBG\alpha LC^{**}(X, Y)$, $WBagLC(X, Y)$, $WBagLC^*(X, Y)$ and $WBagLC^{**}(X, Y)$).

Definition 2.2 Let (A, B) be a subset of $((X, Y, \mathcal{M}))$. Then (A, B) is called a

1. generalized α -locally closed set (briefly $bg^*\alpha$ -lc-set) if $(A, B) = (G, H) \cap (E, F)$, where (G, H) is $bg^*\alpha$ -open and (E, F) is $bg^*\alpha$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.
2. $bg^*\alpha$ -lc*-set if $(A, B) = (G, H) \cap (E, F)$, where (G, H) is $bg^*\alpha$ -open and (E, F) is binary closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.
3. $bg^*\alpha$ -lc**-set if $(A, B) = (G, H) \cap (E, F)$, where (G, H) is binary open and (E, F) is $bg^*\alpha$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.

The collection of all $bg^*\alpha$ -lc-sets (resp. $bg^*\alpha$ -lc*-sets and $bg^*\alpha$ -lc**-sets) of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ will be denoted by $BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$ (resp. $BG^*\alpha LC^*(X, Y)$ and $BG^*\alpha LC^{**}(X, Y)$).

Definition 2.3 Let (A, B) be a subset of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$. Then (A, B) is called a

1. weakly binary generalized α -locally closed set (briefly $wbg^*\alpha$ -lc-set) if $(A, B) = (G, H) \cap (E, F)$, where (G, H) is $wbg^*\alpha$ -open and (E, F) is $wbg^*\alpha$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.
2. $wbg^*\alpha$ -lc*-set if $(A, B) = (G, H) \cap (E, F)$, where (G, H) is $wbg^*\alpha$ -open and (E, F) is binary closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.
3. $wbg^*\alpha$ -lc**-set if $(A, B) = (G, H) \cap (E, F)$, where (G, H) is binary open and (E, F) is $wbg^*\alpha$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.

The class of all $wbg^*\alpha$ -lc-sets (resp. $wbg^*\alpha$ -lc*-sets and $wbg^*\alpha$ -lc**-sets) of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ will be denoted by $WBG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$ (resp. $WBG^*\alpha LC^*(X, Y)$ and $WBG^*\alpha LC^{**}(X, Y)$).

Theorem 2.4 For a binary topological space $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$, the following inclusions hold:

1. $B\alpha LC(X, Y) \subseteq BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$.
2. $BG^*\alpha LC^*(X, Y) \subseteq BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$.
3. $BG^*\alpha LC^{**}(X, Y) \subseteq BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$.

Proof. (1) Assume that $(A, B) \in \alpha LC(X, Y)$. Then $(A, B) = (U, V) \cap (E, F)$, where (U, V) is $b\alpha$ -open and (E, F) is $b\alpha$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$. Since every $b\alpha$ -open set is $bg^*\alpha$ -open and every $b\alpha$ -closed set is $bg^*\alpha$ -closed, we

get (U, V) is $bg^*\alpha$ -open and (E, F) is $bg^*\alpha$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$. Hence $(A, B) \in BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$.

(2) and (3) follow from the fact that every binary closed set is $bg^*\alpha$ -closed and every binary open set is $bg^*\alpha$ -open.

The reverse implications need not be true as seen from the following example:

Example 2.5 Let $X = \{a, b\}$, $Y = \{1, 2\}$ and $\mathcal{M} = \{(\phi, \phi), (\{a\}, \{1\}), (X, Y)\}$. Then

$B\alpha LC(X, Y) = \{(\phi, \phi), (\phi, \{2\}), (\{a\}, \{1\}), (\{a\}, Y), (\{b\}, \phi), (\{b\}, \{2\}), (X, \{1\}), (X, Y)\}$.

$BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y) = \{(\phi, \phi), (\phi, \{1\}), (\phi, \{2\}), (\{a\}, \phi), (\{a\}, \{1\}), (\{a\}, \{2\}), (\{a\}, Y), (\{b\}, \phi), (\{b\}, \{1\}), (\{b\}, \{2\}), (X, \{1\}), (X, Y)\}$

$BG^*\alpha LC^*(X, Y) = \{(\phi, \phi), (\phi, \{2\}), (\{a\}, \{1\}), (\{a\}, Y), (\{b\}, \phi), (\{b\}, \{1\}), (\{b\}, \{2\}), (X, \{1\}), (X, Y)\}$.

$BG^*\alpha LC^{**}(X, Y) = \{(\phi, \phi), (\phi, \{2\}), (\{a\}, \phi), (\{a\}, \{1\}), (\{a\}, \{2\}), (\{a\}, Y), (\{b\}, \phi), (\{b\}, \{2\}), (X, \{1\}), (X, Y)\}$.

Theorem 2.6 Let (A, B) be any subset of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$. If $(A, B) \in BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$, then $(A, B) \in WBG\alpha LC(X, Y)$, $WB\alpha GLC(X, Y)$ and $WBG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$.

Proof. Assume that $(A, B) \in BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$. Then $(A, B) = (U, V) \cap (E, F)$, where (U, V) is $bg^*\alpha$ -open and (E, F) is $bg^*\alpha$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$. Since every $bg^*\alpha$ -open ($bg^*\alpha$ -closed) set is $wbg\alpha$ -open ($wbg\alpha$ -closed), $wbag$ -open ($wbag$ -closed) and $wbg^*\alpha$ -open ($wbg^*\alpha$ -closed), (U, V) is $wbg\alpha$ -open, $wbag$ -open and $wbg^*\alpha$ -open in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ and (E, F) is $wbg\alpha$ -closed, $wbag$ -closed and $wbg^*\alpha$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$. Hence $(A, B) \in WBG\alpha LC(X, Y)$, $WB\alpha GLC(X, Y)$ and $WBG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$.

The reverse implications need not be true as seen from the following example:

Example 2.7 In Example 2.5, then the subset $(X, \{2\})$ is $wbg\alpha$ -lc-set, $wbag$ -lc-set and $wbg^*\alpha$ -lc-set but it is not $bg^*\alpha$ -lc-set.

Remark 2.8 The following examples show that the concept of $BG^*\alpha LC^*(X, Y)$ and $BG^*\alpha LC^{**}(X, Y)$ are independent.

Example 2.9 In Example 2.5, then the subset $(\{b\}, \{1\})$ is $bg^*\alpha\text{-lc}^*$ -set but not $bg^*\alpha\text{-lc}^{**}$ -set and also the subset $(\{a\}, \phi)$ is $bg^*\alpha\text{-lc}^{**}$ -set but not $bg^*\alpha\text{-lc}^*$ -set.

Theorem 2.10 Let (A, B) be any subset of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$, then

1. $BLC(X, Y) \subseteq BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$,
2. $BG^*\alpha LC^*(X, Y) \subseteq BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$,
3. $G^*\alpha LC^*(X, Y) \subseteq WBG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$.

Proof. The proof follows from the fact that every binary closed set is binary α -closed, every binary α -closed set is $bg^*\alpha$ -closed and every $bg^*\alpha$ -closed set is $wbg^*\alpha$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.

The reverse implications need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 2.11 Let $X = \{a, b\}$, $Y = \{1, 2\}$ and $\mathcal{M} = \{(\phi, \phi), (X, \{1\}), (X, Y)\}$. Then

$$BLC(X, Y) = \{(\phi, \phi), (\phi, \{2\}), (X, \{1\}), (X, Y)\}.$$

$$BG^*\alpha LC^*(X, Y) = \{(\phi, \phi), (\phi, \{1\}), (\phi, \{2\}), (\{a\}, \phi), (\{a\}, \{1\}), (\{b\}, \phi), (\{b\}, \{1\}), (X, \phi), (X, \{1\}), (X, Y)\}.$$

$$BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y) = BG^*\alpha LC^{**}(X, Y) = WBG^*\alpha LC(X, Y) = \mathbb{P}(X) \times \mathbb{P}(Y)$$

Definition 2.12 A binary topological space $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is said to be a

1. weakly binary $g\alpha$ -door (briefly $wbg\alpha$ -door) space if each subset of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is either $wbg\alpha$ -open or $wbg\alpha$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.
2. weakly binary αg -door (briefly $wbag$ -door) space if each subset of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is either $wbag$ -open or $wbag$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.
3. binary $g^*\alpha$ -door (briefly $bg^*\alpha$ -door) space if each subset of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is either $wg^*\alpha$ -open or $bg^*\alpha$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.
4. weakly binary $g^*\alpha$ -door (briefly $wbg^*\alpha$) space if each subset of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is either $wbg^*\alpha$ -open or $wbg^*\alpha$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.

Remark 2.13 Let $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ be a binary topological space.

1. If $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is $wbg\alpha$ -door space, then $WBG\alpha LC(X, Y) = \mathbb{P}(X) \times \mathbb{P}(Y)$.
2. If $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is $wbag$ -door space, then $WBA\alpha GLC(X, Y) = \mathbb{P}(X) \times \mathbb{P}(Y)$.
3. If $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is $bg^*\alpha$ -door space, then $BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y) = \mathbb{P}(X) \times \mathbb{P}(Y)$.

4. If $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is $wbg^*\alpha$ -door space, then $WBG^*\alpha LC(X, Y) = \mathbb{P}(X) \times \mathbb{P}(Y)$.

Theorem 2.14 Let $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ be a $bg^*\alpha T_{bc}$ -space. Then the following results hold:

1. $BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y) = BLC(X, Y)$.
2. $BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y) \subseteq BGLC(X, Y)$.
3. $BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y) \subseteq BGLSC(X, Y)$.

Proof. (1) Since $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is a $bg^*\alpha T_{bc}$ -space, every $bg^*\alpha$ -open set is binary open and every $bg^*\alpha$ -closed set is binary closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$. Hence we have $BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y) \subseteq BLC(X, Y)$. By Theorem 2.10, $BLC(X, Y) \subseteq BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$.

Hence $BLC(X, Y) = BG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$. Since $BLC(X, Y) \subseteq BGLC(X, Y)$ and $BLC(X, Y) \subseteq BGLSC(X, Y)$ (1) and (3) follow.

Theorem 2.15 Let $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ be a $wbg^*\alpha T_{bc}$ -space and let (E, F) be a subset of (X, Y) , then the following statements are equivalent:

1. $(E, F) \in WBG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$.
2. $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap wbg^*\alpha\text{-cl}(E, F)$ for some $wbg^*\alpha$ -open set (G, H) .

Proof. (1) $\Rightarrow$ (2) Let $(E, F) \in WBG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$. Then $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap (S, T)$, where (G, H) is $wbg^*\alpha$ -open and (S, T) is $wbg^*\alpha$ -closed in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$. Since $(E, F) \subseteq (G, H)$ and $(E, F) \subseteq wbg^*\alpha\text{-cl}(E, F)$, $(E, F) \subseteq (G, H) \cap wbg^*\alpha\text{-cl}(E, F)$. By the definition of $wbg^*\alpha$ -closure, we have $wbg^*\alpha\text{-cl}(E, F) \subseteq (S, T)$ and hence $(G, H) \cap wbg^*\alpha\text{-cl}(E, F) \subseteq (G, H) \cap (S, T) = (E, F)$. Thus $(G, H) \cap wbg^*\alpha\text{-cl}(E, F) = (E, F)$.

(2) $\Rightarrow$ (1) Assume that $(G, H) \cap wbg^*\alpha\text{-cl}(E, F) = (E, F)$ for some $wbg^*\alpha$ -open set (G, H) . Since $wbg^*\alpha\text{-cl}(E, F)$ is $wbg^*\alpha$ -closed and hence $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap wbg^*\alpha\text{-cl}(E, F) \in WBG^*\alpha LC(X, Y)$.

Theorem 2.16 Let $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ be a $wbg^*\alpha T_{bc}$ -space and let (E, F) be a subset of (X, Y) , then the following statements are equivalent:

1. $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap b\text{-cl}(E, F)$ is $wbg^*\alpha$ -open set (G, H) .
2. $b\text{-cl}(E, F) - (E, F)$ is $wbg^*\alpha$ -closed.

3. $(G, H) = (E, F) \cup ((X, Y) - b-cl(E, F))$ is $wbg^* \alpha$ -open.

Proof. (1) $\Rightarrow$ (2) Let $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap b-cl(E, F)$, for some $wbg^* \alpha$ -open set (G, H) . We have $b-cl(E, F) - (E, F) = b-cl(E, F) \cap (G, H)^c$, $(G, H)^c$ is $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed in (X, Y) , as (G, H) is $wbg^* \alpha$ -open. Since $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is a $wbg^* \alpha T_{bc}$ -space, $(G, H)^c$ is binary closed in (X, Y) . Thus $b-cl(E, F) \cap (G, H)^c$ is binary closed in (X, Y) . Since every binary closed set is $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed, $b-cl(E, F) \cap (G, H)^c$ is $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed in (X, Y) . Hence $b-cl(E, F) - (E, F)$ is $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed in (X, Y) .

(2) $\Rightarrow$ (1) Assume that $b-cl(E, F) - (E, F)$ is $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed. Let $(G, H) = (X, Y) - (b-cl(E, F) - (E, F))$. Then (G, H) is $wbg^* \alpha$ -open and hence $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap b-cl(E, F)$ holds.

(2) $\Rightarrow$ (3) Let $(S, T) = b-cl(E, F) - (E, F)$ be $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed. Then $(X, Y) - (S, T) = (X, Y) - (b-cl(E, F) - (E, F)) = (E, F) \cup ((X, Y) - b-cl(E, F))$. Since (S, T) is $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed, $(X, Y) - (S, T)$ is $wbg^* \alpha$ -open. Thus $(E, F) \cup ((X, Y) - b-cl(E, F))$ is $wbg^* \alpha$ -open.

(3) $\Rightarrow$ (2) Let $(G, H) = (E, F) \cup ((X, Y) - b-cl(E, F))$ be $wbg^* \alpha$ -open. Then $(X, Y) - (G, H) = (X, Y) - ((E, F) \cup ((X, Y) - b-cl(E, F))) = b-cl(E, F) \cap ((X, Y) - (E, F)) = b-cl(E, F) - (E, F)$. Since $(X, Y) - (G, H)$ is $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed, $b-cl(E, F) - (E, F)$ is $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed.

Theorem 2.17 Let (E, F) be a subset of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is a $wbg^* \alpha T_{bc}$ -space. Then $(E, F) \in WBG^* \alpha LC^{**}(X, Y)$ if and only if $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F)$ for some binary open set (G, H) .

Proof. (Necessity) Let $(E, F) \in WBG^* \alpha LC^{**}(X, Y)$. Then $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap (O, P)$, where (G, H) is binary open in (X, Y) and (O, P) is $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed in (X, Y) . Since $(E, F) \subseteq (G, H)$ and $(E, F) \subseteq wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F)$, we have $(E, F) \subseteq (G, H) \cap wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F)$. Since (O, P) is a $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed set containing (E, F) , we have $wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F) \subseteq (O, P)$. This implies $(G, H) \cap wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F) \subseteq (G, H) \cap (O, P) = (E, F)$. Therefore $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F)$.

(Sufficiency) Assume that $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F)$ for some binary

open set (G, H) . Since $wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F)$ is $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed. Hence we have $(E, F) \in WBG^* \alpha LC^{**}(X, Y)$.

Theorem 2.18 For a $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed subset (E, F) of a binary topological space $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ the following statements are equivalent:

1. $(E, F) \in BG^* \alpha LC(X, Y)$.
2. $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F)$ for some $wbg^* \alpha$ -open set (G, H) in (X, Y) .

Proof. (1) $\Rightarrow$ (2) Let $(E, F) \in BG^* \alpha LC(X, Y)$. Then there exists a $wbg^* \alpha$ -open subset (G, H) and a $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed subset (O, P) of (X, Y) such that $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap (O, P)$. Since $(E, F) \subseteq (G, H)$ and $(E, F) \subseteq wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F)$, $(E, F) \subseteq (G, H) \cap wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F)$. Conversely, by definition of $wbg^* \alpha$ -closure, $wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F) \subseteq (O, P)$ and hence $(G, H) \cap wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F) \subseteq (G, H) \cap (O, P) = (E, F)$. Therefore $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F)$.

(2) $\Rightarrow$ (1) Assume that $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F)$ for some $wbg^* \alpha$ -open set (G, H) . Since $wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F)$ is $wbg^* \alpha$ -closed and hence $(E, F) = (G, H) \cap wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F) \in BG^* \alpha LC(X, Y)$.

Definition 2.19 A subset (E, F) of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is called

1. $wbg \alpha$ -dense if $wbg \alpha-cl(E, F) = (X, Y)$.
2. $wbag$ -dense if $wbag-cl(E, F) = (X, Y)$.
3. $wbg^* \alpha$ -dense if $wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F) = (X, Y)$.
4. $wbg^* \alpha$ -dense if $wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F) = (X, Y)$.

Theorem 2.20 For a binary topological space $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$, the following results hold:

1. Every $wbg^* \alpha$ -dense set is binary dense.
2. Every $wbg^* \alpha$ -dense set is $wbg^* \alpha$ -dense.

Proof. 1. Assume that (E, F) is a $wbg^* \alpha$ -dense set. Then $wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F) = (X, Y)$. Obviously, $b-cl(E, F) \subseteq (X, Y)$. Since $wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F) \subseteq b-cl(E, F)$, $b-cl(E, F) \supseteq wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F) = (X, Y)$. Hence $b-cl(E, F) = (X, Y)$. Therefore (E, F) is binary dense.

2. Assume that (E, F) is a $wbg^* \alpha$ -dense set. Then $wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F) = (X, Y)$. Obviously, $wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F) \subseteq (X, Y)$. Since $wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F) \subseteq wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F)$, which implies $wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F) \supseteq wbg^* \alpha-cl(E, F)$.

$cl(E, F) = (X, Y)$. Hence $bg^*\alpha-cl(E, F) = (X, Y)$.

Therefore (E, F) is $bg^*\alpha$ -dense.

The converses of the above Theorem need not be true as seen from the following examples:

Example 2.21 Let $X = \{1, 2\}$, $Y = \{a, b\}$ and $\mathcal{M} = \{(\phi, \phi), (\phi, \{b\}), (\{1\}, \{a\}), (\{1\}, Y), (X, Y)\}$. Then the subset $(\{2\}, Y)$ is binary dense but not $bg^*\alpha$ -dense.

Example 2.22 Let $X = \{a, b\}$, $Y = \{1, 2\}$ and $\mathcal{M} = \{(\phi, \phi), (\{a\}, \{1\}), (\{b\}, \{2\}), (X, Y)\}$. Then the subset $(\{b\}, \{1\})$ is $bg^*\alpha$ -dense but not $wbg^*\alpha$ -dense.

Theorem 2.23 Let $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ be a binary topological space.

Then

1. Every $wbg\alpha$ -dense set is a $bg^*\alpha$ -dense set.
2. Every $wbag$ -dense set is also a $bg^*\alpha$ -dense set.

proof . Similar to Theorem 2.20.

Definition 2.24 A binary topological space $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is called

1. $wbg\alpha$ -submaximal if every $wbg\alpha$ -dense subset is $wbg\alpha$ -open in (X, Y) .
2. $wbag$ -submaximal if every $wbag$ -dense subset is $wbag$ -open in (X, Y) .
3. $bg^*\alpha$ -submaximal if every $bg^*\alpha$ -dense subset is $bg^*\alpha$ -open in (X, Y) .
4. $wbg^*\alpha$ -submaximal if every $wbg^*\alpha$ -dense subset is $wbg^*\alpha$ -open in (X, Y) .

Theorem 2.25 Let $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ be a binary topological space.

If (X, Y) is binary submaximal, then it is also $bg^*\alpha$ -submaximal.

Proof. Let (E, F) be a $bg^*\alpha$ -dense subset of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$. By Theorem 2.20, (E, F) is binary dense in $((X, Y, \mathcal{M}))$. Since (X, Y) is binary submaximal, (E, F) is binary open. Then (E, F) is $bg^*\alpha$ -open, as every binary open set is $bg^*\alpha$ -open. Hence (X, Y) is $bg^*\alpha$ -submaximal.

The converse of the above Theorem need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 2.26 Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $Y = \{1, 2\}$ and $\mathcal{M} = \{(\phi, \phi), (\{a\}, \{1\}), (\{b\}, \phi), (\{b\}, \{2\}), (\{a, b\}, \{1\}), (\{a, b\}, Y), (X, Y)\}$. Then $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is $bg^*\alpha$ -submaximal but not binary submaximal, since the

subset $(\{a, b\}, \{2\})$ is binary dense but not binary open in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.

Theorem 2.27 Let $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ be a binary topological space.

If (X, Y) is $bg^*\alpha$ -submaximal, then it is $wbg^*\alpha$ -submaximal also.

Proof. Let (E, F) be a $wbg^*\alpha$ -dense subset of $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$. By Theorem 2.20, (E, F) is $bg^*\alpha$ -dense in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$. Since (X, Y) is $bg^*\alpha$ -submaximal, (E, F) is $bg^*\alpha$ -open. Since every $bg^*\alpha$ -open set is $wbg^*\alpha$ -open, (E, F) is $wbg^*\alpha$ -open. Hence (X, Y) is $wbg^*\alpha$ -submaximal.

The converse of the above Theorem need not be true as seen from the following example.

Example 2.28 In Example 2.22, then $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ is $wbg^*\alpha$ -submaximal but not $bg^*\alpha$ -submaximal, since the subset $(\{a\}, \{2\})$ is $bg^*\alpha$ -dense but not $bg^*\alpha$ -open in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$.

Theorem 2.29 Let $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$ be a binary topological space.

If (X, Y) is $bg^*\alpha$ -submaximal, then (X, Y) is both $wbg\alpha$ -submaximal and $wbag$ -submaximal.

Proof. Since every $wbg\alpha$ -dense set and $wbag$ -dense set is also $bg^*\alpha$ -dense and since every $bg^*\alpha$ -open set is both $wbg\alpha$ -open and $wbag$ -open in $(X, Y, \mathcal{M})$, the proof follows.

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